

Pattern of work related musculoskeletal pain among tricycle drivers in Kano metropolis, Nigeria

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Abstract

Musculoskeletal disorders have deleterious effect that produces disability among the workers, therefore, this study was carried out to investigate the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among commercial tricycle drivers (CTCDs) operating within Kano metropolis, Kano State, Nigeria. A total of 384 CTCDs participated in this study, and were recruited using purposive sampling technique in this cross sectional survey. The data were collected using Modified Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ). Descriptive statistics of frequency/ percentage and inferential statistic of Pearson correlation were used to summarize the data and SPSS version 16 were used for analysis alpha was set at 0.05.

All the participants (100%) were males between the ages of 19-67 years and the results obtained showed that majority of which (65%) falls between 19-29 years. Most of the participants were single (66.9%) and 81.5% of the participants never attended formal school.

The most common part of the body frequently reported with pains in the past 12 months is ankle with 106 participants (18.4%) while on the past 7 days, 76 participants (18.6%) reported hips/thighs/buttocks as most area affected when carrying out their activity. The outcome of this study revealed that there was a significant relationship between the frequently reported musculoskeletal pain (ankle pain) and the duration of work ($P < 0.05$). The study also revealed that there was a significant relationship between characteristics pain that limits activities of daily living (low back pain) in the past 12 months and duration of work ($P < 0.05$).

Keywords: Work related musculoskeletal pains (WRMSP), Work related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSD), commercial tricycle drivers (CTDs), pattern.

Introduction

Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) are group of painful disorders that affect the soft tissues of various joints such as neck, shoulder, elbow, hand, wrist, knee, and foot which depends on the type of activity one is involved [1]. The disorders can be inflammatory or degenerative type affecting various tissues and joints due to a single or cumulative trauma [2] [3].

Work related musculoskeletal pain (WRMSP) as defined by Canadian Center for Occupational Health and Safety is a painful disorder affecting muscles, tendon, nerves caused by occupational activities which are associated with frequent and repetitive postures [4] The World Health Organization (WHO) recognizes those disorders as work-related when the work activities and work conditions significantly contribute to their development or exacerbation but are not the sole determinant of causation [5].

Prevalence of MSDs becomes increasingly common throughout the world during the past decades [6]. Among professional truck drivers in the United Kingdom,

MSP has been reported to be 81% [7] while prevalence of 77% among occupational drivers in Oyo state, Nigeria has been reported [8]. Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMD) affect workers in many occupations including vehicle drivers [9]. WRMSD can affect almost all parts of the body especially the back, neck and upper limbs, depending upon the physical movement characteristics, and the ergonomic and mechanical design of work tasks [9]. Musculoskeletal disorders have deleterious effect that produces disability among the workers with considerable financial consequences due to workers compensation and medical expenses [6]. The factors that contribute to the MSD may include prolonged sitting, poor postures, exposure to whole-body vibration, long driving time, heavy lifting, manual materials handling, poor diet or other psychosocial factors [7][10]. Commercial tricycle driving has not been a prominent occupation in Kano metropolis not until year 2012 when the Kano state government banned commercial motorcycle driving in the state (due to security challenges) and since from then, CTDs are all over the metropolitan area in Kano. Therefore, this study

focused on investigating the pattern of work related musculoskeletal pains and relationship with some risk factors among commercial tricycles drivers in Kano metropolis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS
Participants

The participants for this study include commercial tricycle drivers operating within Kano metropolis and were recruited using purposive sampling technique. The research design deployed for this study was a cross sectional survey and all tricycle drivers that have work for at least 12 months duration were included while those with history of trauma and diagnosis of degenerative joint disease were excluded.

Instrument
Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire

Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire was used as the assessment tool for this study, it comprises of questions inquiring about troubles encountered around the nine human body areas defined (neck, shoulders, upper back, lower back, elbows, wrists, thighs, knees and ankles). The table requests a yes' or 'no' response for each body area to three questions concerning annual prevalence, weekly prevalence and annual disability. Other sections were incorporated to assess socio-demographic variables (Age, gender, marital status, tribe, and highest educational qualification) and information about the nature of the occupation (work duration, years of work experience, and work posture)

Procedure

Consent was sought and obtained from the participants before the commencement of the study, the procedure and nature of the study were explained to the partic-

ipants prior to the commencement of the study. The questionnaires were administered to the participants and later retrieved. Five hundred (500) questionnaires were administered but only three hundred and eighty four (384) were retrieved indicating 77% response.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics of frequencies, mean, standard deviation, tables and charts were used to summarize the data. The data was analyzed using inferential statistics of Pearson correlation at an alpha level of 0.05 with Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 16

RESULTS:

A total number of three hundred and eighty four (384) tricycle drivers participated in this study. The participants recruited were between the ages of 19-67 years and all the 384 (100%) were males, majority of which 257 (66.9%) are single while 121 (31.5%) are married. Majority of them never attended school 313(81.5%) while only 15 (3.9%) of them had attended tertiary institution Table 1 above shows the demographic characteristics of the participants with 100% Males and majority within the ages of 19-29, mostly singles and over 80% have not attended any formal education Table 2: Differences in step length, stride length and walking speed between baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks Post-intervention in the control and experimental groups The table below described the characteristics of the occupation were 197(51.3%) work for 5-8 hours per day, 331 (86.2%) work for about 5-6 days per week while all 384 (100%) fully carried out their occupational activity in sitting position

Table 1 showing Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants

Variables	n	%
AGE (YEARS)		
19-29	248	64.6
30-39	100	26.0
40-49	31	8.1
50-59	4	1.0
60 and Above	1	0.3
Mean Age	29.84±0.03	
GENDER		
Male	384	100
Female	0	0
MARITAL STATUS		
Single	257	66.9
Marrried	121	31.5
Divorced	6	1.6
Widow	0	0
EDUCATION		
Never attended	313	81.5
Primary	35	9.1
Secondary	21	5.5
Tertiary	15	3.9

Key: n= frequency, %= percentage

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage of risk factors of MSP among the tricycle drivers

Variables	n	%
Working hours per day		
1-4	28	7.3
5-8	197	51.3
9-12	127	33.1
12 & above	32	8.3
Working days per week		
1-2	0	0
3-4	26	6.8
5-6	331	86.2
Daily	27	7
Nature of work		
Repetitive & vibratory	360	93.8
Forceful	24	6.2
Handling heavy loads	0	0
Work Posture		
Sitting	384	100
Kneeling	0	0
Standing	0	0
Total	384	100

Key: n= frequency, %= percentage

Table 3 Pattern of musculoskeletal pain at different body parts in the past 12 months

The table 3 below is showing the total number of pain reported at different body parts in the last 12 months, with the ankle pain having the highest report 106 (18.4%) while hips/thigh/buttocks pain were reported 34(5.9%)

Variables	n	%
Neck	67	11.6
Shoulder	70	12.2
Elbow	53	9.2
Wrists/hands	45	7.8
Upper back	60	10.4
Lower back	60	10.4
Hips/thigh/buttocks	34	5.9
Knees	81	14.1
Ankles	106	18.4

Key: n= frequency, %= percentage

Table 4 Pattern of musculoskeletal pain at different body parts in the past 7 days

The table below is showing the total number of pain reported at different body parts in the past 7 days. The hips/thigh/buttocks pain were reported the highest as 18.6% while the lowest region reported were the shoulders with 1.7%

Variables	n	%
Neck	10	2.4
Shoulders	7	1.7
Elbows	53	13
Wrists/hands	45	11
Upper back	60	14.7
Lower back	52	12.7
Hips/thigh/buttocks	76	18.6
Knees	56	13.7
Ankles	50	12.2

Key: n= frequency, %= percentage

Table 5: Musculoskeletal Pain at different body parts frequently restricting Activities of Daily Living (ADL) over the last 12 month

The table shows the results of musculoskeletal pain at different body parts frequently restricting activity of daily living over the last 12 months. Up to 137(31.8%) of participants acknowledged that lower back pain prevented them from ADL while the hips/thigh/buttocks, knee and ankles pain had the least frequency 1.2%

Variables	n	%
Neck	55	12.7
Shoulder	63	14.6
Elbows	35	8
Wrists/hands	86	20
Upper back	40	9.3
Lower back	137	31.8
Hips/thighs/buttocks	5	1.2
Knees	5	1.2
Ankles	5	1.2

Key: n= frequency, %= percentage

Table 6.0 Relationship between Musculoskeletal pain (Ankle pains) and characteristics of participant/ work in the last 12 months
In the table below, Pearson correlation showed that there was a significant relationship between ankle pain and working hours per day in the last 12 months

Variables	P- value
Nature of work	0.270
Hours of work per day	0.000*
Level of Education	0.520
Age	0.244

Key: *= significant at p< 0.05

Table 7 Relationship between ADL restriction due to Musculoskeletal (low back pain) and characteristics of participant/ work in the last 12 months

In Table 7 Pearson correlation showed that there was a significant relationship between the hours of work per day and the restriction of ADL due to musculoskeletal low back pain within the last 12 months with the P value at 0.000.

Table7. Activities Restricted by Low back pain with the last 12 months

Variables	P- value
Hours of work per day	0.000*
Nature of work	0.940
Age	0.244

Key: *= significant at p< 0.05

DISCUSSION:

Musculoskeletal disorders have deleterious effect that produces disability among the workers, therefore this study investigated the pattern of musculoskeletal disorders among the tricycle drivers in Kano metropolis. A total number of three hundred and eighty four (384) tricycle drivers participated in this study within the age range of 19-67 years and all 384(100%) were males, majority of which 257 (66.9%) are single while 121 (31.5%) are married and 313(81.5%) never attended school

The result of this study revealed all 384 (100%) the commercial tricycle drivers in Kano metropolis as males thus making it similar to other Nigerian studies conducted that revealed driving occupation as males only job [8][9][11] this may not be unrelated with the culture where driving is seen as a job not compatible with ladies (especially in Northern part of the country where this study was carried out).

Majority of the participants 197(51.3%) work for 5-8 hours per day and 331 (86.2%) work for about 5-6 days per week while all 384 (100%) fully carried out their occupational activity in sitting position. This is in line with the finding of Ojoet *al* in Nigeria who conducted a study on taxi drivers and the participants were found to work for about 8 hours in a day [8]

The age groups with the highest reporting of MSPs were between 19-29 years and the mean age of the participants 29.84±0.03 which falls within young adults categories, this is contrary to the finding of Akinpeluet *al* and Ojoet *al* [8][9] where professional drivers fall within the middle aged groups, this may be due to the fact that young adults have passion for tricycle driving in Kano which is more of a fashion and the likelihood for young adults to dominate the job. The most common part of the body frequently reported with pains in the past 12 months is ankle among

106(18.4%), this could be due to the nature of continuous process of applying brake to decelerate the tricycle while on the past 7 days, 76 (18.6%) reported hips/thighs/buttocks as most area affected when carrying out their activity

The outcome of this study revealed that there was a significant relationship between the frequently reported musculoskeletal pain (ankle pain) and the duration of work, this is in accordance with the finding of the study by Reed et al which stated that strain, overuse and repetitive activities may result in chronic foot and ankle pain [12]. But no significant relationship was observed between ankle pains and age as well as level of education, this is in contrast with the finding of Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) in 1997 that lack of education, training and knowledge would result to musculoskeletal pain [13] while Gholaniet *al* further stated that there is a significant relationship between age (over 40 years) and musculoskeletal pain [14].

Another outcome of this study showed that there was a significant relationship between characteristics pain that limits activities of daily living (low back pain) in the past 12 months and duration of work this is supported by studies that suggested sitting for extended periods daily could be a risk factor for musculoskeletal pain especially that of low back [15][16][17][18]

CONCLUSION

From the results of the study, it can be concluded that, among CTDs, musculoskeletal pain reflects in the acute period as hip/thighs/buttocks pains while in the chronic period it presents mostly as ankle pain. The MSP affects the performance of commercial tricycle drivers in terms of duration of work, the longer the duration the more the risk of musculoskeletal pain

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results obtained from this study, the following recommendations were made; further studies should incorporate wider sample size and remote areas of the state. Since the majority commercial tricycle drivers

are young, single and uneducated, this necessitates the need for awareness campaign for knowledge of ergonomics as it relates to the occupation such as seat designs, posture and duration of sitting

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.